

WOMEN'S LEADERSHIP AND DEVELOPMENT IN RURAL HIMACHAL PRADESH

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Abstract

In this paper an attempt has been made to study the women's leadership and development in rural Himachal Pradesh. In rural areas the presence of women in leadership roles promotes sustainable development and inclusive growth. Although women face obstacles in decision-making and leadership, rural women in Himachal Pradesh make substantial contribution to agriculture, local economy and governance. Himachal Pradesh is one of the state which implemented many policies to enhance leadership role of women such as 50% reservation in Panchayati Raj Institutions. However, the question remains whether these provisions actually enhancing the role of women in leadership at rural areas. The present paper aims to assess the participation of women in leadership roles, within rural governance, to study the impact of government initiatives to promoting women's leadership roles.

Keywords: *Women in leadership, Sustainable development, Inclusive growth, Panchayati Raj Institutions.*

Introduction

The advancement of women in the world is intimately related to the country's progress. Just 25 years ago, there was a lot of evidence of gender discriminations in the jobs, in homes, and even in the high education. Women had to overcome these obstacles and pursue possibilities that would place them on an equal basis with man. The realization of human wants and ambitions is the primary goal of progress. There are many barriers such as food, clothing, shelter and employment facing by poor countries in the way of their progress. Every

individual have the right to fulfill their ambitions for better life. Poverty and inequalities in the world increase the risk of environment and other crises. Sustainable development attempts to achieve peace between humanity and nature (Brundtland, 1987). It is highlighted in the *World Bank's 2012 World Development Report: Gender Equality and Development* that it is necessary to reduce gender disparities for policymaking and development. The key areas of reducing gender inequality are: (1) minimizing the disparity between men and women in the society, (2) reducing the gender disparity in terms of production, pay, and financial prospects, (3) making decision about their life, and (4) reducing gender disparity from passed down through the generations. Humanity may achieve sustainable development that meets current demands without risking future generations' ability to meet their own demands (Brundtland, 1987). It addresses the demands of both men and women. Sustainable development has four interconnected aspects of development: economic, social, cultural, and environment preservation. Gender equality required a comprehensive and integrated approach, so that women can empower in the all aspects of development (**Warth & Koparova, 2012**). In order to promote socioeconomic development and the accomplishment of the Sustainable development Goals, this is necessary to putting on elevating women to prominent roles. This strategy acknowledges reduce gender inequality and enhance the participation of women in the development activities. Empowering women is a process that includes both creating a non-discriminating environment for women and enhancing their ability to take charge of their lives; so that women can make necessary changes in the family and society. Collaborative actions are required by the government, community, and the non-government organizations. Equal participation of the women in the all sectors, policy areas, control in the resources and in the level of implementations of the policies, are required. Women in the leadership role is a development strategy in which women assume leadership positions and actively contribute to influencing and advancing a community's social, political, and economic development. In this strategy, women are not merely recipients of progress of the nation rather they play a role as leaders who equally contributed to the planning and decision-making. However, outside of academia, leadership in sustainable development is still primarily viewed as gender neutral. The example of this issue was seen in the almost completely male list of prior receipts of the World Sustainable Development Summit's Sustainable Development Award (Shinbrot et al., 2019). Women play a crucial role not only in the family, community, and in the society but also in the economy and politics. It is necessary to support laws that advance gender equality and give women

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more chance to forefront as the leaders; this new point of view recognise women's socioeconomic and political participation. Women led development is needed for the promoting economic growth, eliminate gender disparity, National progress, and for achieve Sustainable Development Goals. Women-led development is essential in Indian context because it has the capability to significantly boost growth, improve social well-being, encourage women's entrepreneurship and for achieving sustainable development; as it allows the women to actively participate in decision making, workforce, eliminates gender inequality.

Government Initiatives for Women's Leadership Role in India

India has acknowledged the vital roles that women play in social advancement, economic success, and equal roles in achieving sustainable development. Prime Minister Narendra Modi emphasised the importance of women's engagement in global development the G20 Summit in Bali. For removing the inequalities that currently limit the opportunities of women in education, employment, leadership roles etc. women led development is necessary in India. The Himachal Pradesh government has taken a number of steps to increase women's involvement in governance and leadership roles. One of the most important steps was 50% reservation for women in Panchayati Raj Institutions (Department of Pachayati Raj, Government of Himachal Pradesh). Participation of women in local government has increased due to this initiative. In rural Himachal Pradesh women make substantial contribution to agriculture, the local economy, and community welfare. However the representation in leadership roles had been constrained by many socio-cultural barriers like inadequate leadership training opportunities (Chaudhary & Sharma, 2019). In order to promote gender equality and encourage inclusive and sustainable development, leadership role of women at the grassroots level is essential. It is the key driver of rural development, economic empowerment, and for social change. Women especially for rural areas are continue to struggling to recognize the importance of remunerated talents and decision making, underlining the need of financial independence for women. Recognising the obstacles faced by women especially in rural areas government of India launched a number of transformative efforts to realize their potential for national development. One of the most significant initiatives has been made by the Gender disparity in the rural areas is the biggest obstacle in the leadership of women. It is due to following traditional social norms.

- Women is not receiving quality education in rural areas due to lack of education institutions
- Job opportunities and wage disparity are constraints in the way of economic development of the women.
- Lack of awareness about the rights and provisions related to women.
- Vulnerability against women is the obstacle which restricts women to their growth.
- Male dominance in the leadership roles
- Poor healthcare services

Reviews of the Related Literature

The review of related literature reveals that Subramaniam (2003) found the role of women in development and emphasised on developing abilities in the context of training and networking efforts. Capacity building and change can serve as a feasible way to promote courage and confidence among underprivileged women. Warth & Koparova (2012) examined women's empowerment as a critical step to achieving gender equality and as a result, sustainable development. The study focused to the subject of what needs to be done for empowering women. Creating an enabling policy environment and strengthening women's ability as active agents of change for sustainable development. Gupta (2013) analysed the obstacles of women led entrepreneurs and shortcomings of policy making. Study found that the gender disparity was the biggest problem of entrepreneurial endeavours in India. Study highlighted that promoting factors of women led enterprises were educational achievements and women's income generating activities. Study suggested the need for modification in policy focus to address gender inequality and built leadership skills and professional abilities for women. Shinbrot et al (2019) investigated the barriers women faced for becoming leaders to achieve sustainable development goals. By qualitative analysis of the interviews of 120 women and men, found that: i). male dominance structures of the society were preventing women from becoming leaders. ii). some complicated and unseen factors like uncertainty, self-doubt, timidity, hesitancy etc. and also gender inequalities were hindering the leadership role of women. Chaudhary and Sharma (2019) examine women's participation in Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) in Himachal Pradesh, mainly focus on the scope, nature and difficulties faced by women in rural governance. The study highlighted that the 73rd Constitutional Amendment, which reserve seats for women in PRIs and significantly increased their role in numerical participation in governance. However, author highlighted

the challenges like lack of political awareness, societal barriers and lack of access to resources, etc were restrict women's active participation in politics and leadership in the governance. Gupta et al (2024) examined the shortcomings in advancement of women in rural areas and with special emphasis in skill development and earning of women. Study stated that employment creation programmes and skill development may help to achieve Sustainable Development Goals. Study suggested to removing the policy implementation challenges through recognising the value of talent, using it for decision making and awareness of the skill. Women's leadership in rural governance is widely recognised as a cornerstone for inclusive growth, and sustainable community development (United Nations, 2020). Although women have historically made substantial contributions to social welfare, local economies, and agriculture in Himachal Pradesh, they are still underrepresented in leadership positions within Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) and other governing bodies (Chaudhary & Sharma, 2019). There is still a disconnect between policy provisions and the reality on the ground, even with state-level initiatives and constitutional regulations like the 73rd Constitution Amendment Act, which requires the reservation of seats for women in PRIs (Ministry of Panchayati Raj, 2023). The significance of the present study lies in its potential to inform policymakers, stakeholders, Non-Government Organisations about the strategies needed to strengthen women's participation, and their leadership in political decision-making.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the participation of women in leadership roles, within rural governance in Himachal Pradesh.
- To study the impact of government initiatives to promoting women's leadership roles.

Delimitations of the Study: The study was delimited to district Shimla of Himachal Pradesh Only. Data was collected from women Pradhans from selected blocks from district Shimla.

Methodology

Descriptive survey method was used in the study. In this paper data from primary and secondary sources were collected. Primary data was collected with the help of questionnaire by conducting field survey in District Shimla in Himachal Pradesh. The secondary data was collected from different sources like reports of different government departments, research reports, research paper, articles, press release and data from internet sources etc. Shimla is the Capital of Himachal Pradesh and constitute the 75 % of rural population (as per census

2011). Women in Shimla District contribute in the economic activities and in the governance. Shimla District offers a representative context to study women's leadership and empowerment at the grassroot. Therefore, district Shimla selected purposively for the study. In Shimla there are 412 Gram Panchayats exists in 13 Development Block (District Panchayat Office, Shimla). Hundred women Pradhans were selected conveniently from the 13 development blocks for the study. The distribution of the sample is given in the Table-1. The data collected from women Pradhans has analysed with percentage analysis.

Table-1 Distribution of the Sample

District	Development block	Total number of Gram Panchayat	Number of gram Panchayats selected that are Headed by women Pradhan
Shimla	Mashobra	30	8
	Basantpur	24	10
	Chopal	48	9
	Chhohara	32	10
	Rohru	37	7
	Jubal	25	8
	Kotkhari	26	10
	Theog	59	10
	Rampur	37	6
	Narkhari	17	3
	Narkanda	28	5
	Kupvi	15	4
	Tutu	34	10
Total		412	100

Analysis and Interpretation of data

The analysis of the data is given below

1. Participation of women in leadership roles, within rural governance in Himachal Pradesh.

1.1 Personal Profile of the Respondents is given in the Table-2

Table-2, Personal Profile of the Respondents

Age of the Respondents		
Age (in years)	Frequency (Total number of respondents=100)	Percentage (%)
21-30	12	12%
31-45	54	54%
46-60	30	30%
Above 61 years	2	2%
Educational Qualification		
Illiterate	Nil	-
Below metric	3	3%
Metric	43	43%
Secondary (+2)	30	30%
Graduation	13	13%
Above graduation	11	11%

From Table-2, it reveals that majority (54%) of respondents belong to the age group of 31-45 years and 30% respondents belong to 45-60 years. Less participation has been seen at the age group of 21-30 and above 60 years. This indicates that middle age group of women mostly participated in the grassroots governance. In the educational qualification 43% respondents have education up to metric level and 30% completed secondary education graduation and above together make 24% education level. Only 3% are below metric and there are no illiterate respondents.

Table-3, Participation of Women in Leadership Roles

Sr. No.	Responses	Yes		No	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	First time Elected as Pradhan	68	68%	32	32%
2	Elected through general election	5	5%	95	95%
3	Elected through reserved seats for women	95	95%	5	5%
4	Self-motivated candidature	43	43%	56	56%

5	Independent decision making in Panachayat meetings	62	62%	38	38%
6	Community support your role as leader	77	77%	23	23%
7	Attended any leadership training programme	100	100%	Nil	-

Table - 3 shows that a majority (68%) of women elected first time as Pradhan, 32% respondents may elected more than one time as Pradhan. 95% of respondents elected in the reserved seat for women, this indicates that women participation ensure due to the reservation seat in PRIs. 43% respondents decided to contest election on their own whereas 56% motivated by family or community. 62% reported independent decision making whereas, 38% still rely on others for their decisions. 77% reported community acceptance for their role as leader while 23 % still face obstacle as leader. All the respondents attended training leadership programmes, as the government has made it compulsory.

Table-4, Impact of Government Initiatives to Promoting Women’s Leadership Roles

Sr.	Responses	Yes		No	
		Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Helpful to build confidence among women	100	100%	Nil	-
2.	Ensuring women positions in decision making	100	100%	Nil	-
3.	Community acceptance for women leaders	76	76%	24	24%
4.	Improvement in decision making skills at home and community	61	61%	39	39%
5.	Motivating to participate in higher level of politics	55	55%	45	45%

From Table - 4, it is found that all respondents felt that their leadership role helped to build confidence among themselves, and ensure women presence in the decision making. A majority (76%) felt accepted by the community as leader, whereas 24% respondents did not; this indicates socio-cultural resistance to the acceptance of women in leader roles. 61% respondents experienced improved decision making skills at home and in the community, the remaining 39% suggest that capacity building programmes still need to improve. Slightly more than half were motivated to participate in politics in higher level, however 45% still face barriers in it.

Findings of the Study

The following are the findings of this paper;

- It is found that majority of the women respondents were belonging to the middle age group that is 31-45 years which are active in grassroot politics. Education level of women Pradhan were good as there was no illiterate respondents find. And basic school education (metric and +2) were completed by the respondents.
- 68% were elected first time as Pradhan which means new entrants into leadership position.
- 95% women respondents were elected through reserved seats which indicating the importance of reservation policy at grassroot level.
- Community and family influence were seen in the women contested in election, which was seen in the response of 56% respondents. While 43% contested elections on their own initiatives.
- Majority (62%) of respondents reported independently decision making while 38% shows partial autonomy in leadership roles. 77% felt accepted by the community as leader but 23% still face socio cultural resistance.
- Training for leadership or capacity building is compulsory for elected PRIs, all the respondents' women Pradhan attended these training programme.
- Positive impact of 50% reservation of the seat for women in terms of built confidence, ensured women's presence in governance.
- 61% reported skill development in decision making at home and in the community. 55% motivated in higher level of politics after entering in grassroot level.

Conclusion

To promote socioeconomic growth and to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals, it is vital to elevate women to prominent positions. Women must participate equally in all sectors and policy areas, as well as have control over resources and the level of policy execution. The process in which women occupy in leadership roles and actively contribute to social, economic and political success is called women led development. Women led development is required to promote economic progress, eradicate gender disparities, and meet the Sustainable Development Goals especially leadership role of women at the grassroots level. \ However, other issues such as gender inequality, education, and socio-economic, political status continue to be difficult to address. To overcome these barriers to women-led development, quality education, health services, women's safety should be prioritized, employment opportunities should be raised.

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